

**ENGLISH WRITING MATERIALS BASED ON NEEDS FOR EFL
STUDENTS.**

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Annotation: The thesis gives the information about the writing materials which English language teachers are recommended to write their own supplementary material based on local needs. The evaluation showed that besides the good points, there were still a number of weak points. The final product was completed as teachers know their students' needs.

Keywords: learning needs, writing material, remote data

Introduction

Students from remote area schools often show very different competence of English than of urban ones. The remote schools are not like the urban one are not completed with such facilities as reference books, language lab, competent teachers, and English club. However, they must teach the students the same standard of achievement. The students merely rely on textbooks offered by the government. Schools that have the English language teachers in remote areas also merely rely upon the textbooks provided by the government or commercial publishers. It shows that textbooks play an important role in the classroom. Sheldon cited in Litz (2005, p. 5) argues, “The textbooks not only represent the visible heart of any ELT program but also offer considerable advantages – for both the students and the teachers”. Sheldon cited in Litz (2005, p. 8) writes that ELT textbooks is end-product of an author's or a publisher's desire for quick profit. Thus, English language subject in the remote area schools is hard to teach. It is because the authors do not know the real conditions of the students. Thus, it is common to have the students can not even write a sentence in English language. Students demand appropriate textbooks from the remote area schools for their level of competence. It is the teacher's job also to write their own

supplementary material to help the students learn well. Writing is one of the four language skills.

Main investigation

This skill may enable the students to understand language. Unfortunately, the writing skill of the second year students' skill is still low. It is because students' low competence in writing skill. The students get difficulties in finding and generating ideas; they feel confused to start their writing; and, they have low motivation in writing. McDonough & Shaw (2005, p.154) argue that writing for most of us only happens to any significant extent as part of formal education. Students write only when they go to school. They write because the formal education system forces them to write as one of the requirements of the standard competence. Students' cultural background also influences students' writing. Hyland (2009, p.54, p. 78) urges, “This is partly because our cultural values are reflected in and carried through language”, and “they are likely to have their own ideas of what ‘good writing’ consists of based on their prior culture and social experiences”.

Liebman cited in Hyland (2009, p. 54) remarks about students' experiences by claiming, “We must also determine what these students' prior experiences are”. Writing is linked to cultural background, prior knowledge and prior experience. There are some reasons why writing is significant skill in language teaching and learning. Harmer (1998, p. 79) classifies the reasons into: reinforcement, language development, learning style and writing as a skill. In reinforcement, students acquire language in a purely oral/aural way, but most of the students benefit greatly from seeing the language written down. In language development, students need to develop four language skills. They are listening, reading, speaking and writing. At least students can write simple sentence in English at elementary level (Raimes 1983, p. 4).

Tomlinson (2003, p. 18) claims, “Language learners succeed best if learning is a positive, relaxed and enjoyable”. Thus, teachers need to create learning activities in the classroom which are: positive, relaxed and enjoyable. Because of the textbooks are difficult for the level of students' competence in remote areas, thus, a teacher must be

creative to design or develop his own materials or in-house materials (Bocanegra, 2010, p. 150). McGrath (2002, p. 84) states that teachers know their own students and will be able to ‘tune’ the material to suit their level, their aptitude, their interests, their needs, and personalise it so that it seems even more meaningful. Thus, teachers may develop or simplify the textbooks by looking their students’ needs. The existing textbook may not accomplish the needs of the students in learning English, thus, a supplementary material may help to fulfill the needs. In remote area schools, a textbook becomes the primary source. Needs of students in learning is very important to fulfill. If the material cannot fulfill the needs of students, the learning process will not achieve the goal. The students cannot learn well and even they do not have motivation to study. Because of the importance of the needs, Masuhara (2011, p. 238) defines “needs” as: 1) ownership (whose needs they are), 2) kinds (what kinds of needs are identified), and 3) sources (what the sources for the needs are). Because the focus of this present study is about the students or learners, the learners’ needs will be the core in the writing material that base on the local needs.

Conclusion in remote area, by exploring local needs such as students’ everyday activities, students’ hobbies, students’ experiences and students’ surroundings can be good sources for designing a teaching material. It was proved by positive feedbacks from the students in the implementation. The product of Happy Writing Material was validated by subject matter expert, educational expert, and local culture expert. The product can be categorized as good product and can be used in the learning activities.

REFERENCES

1. Bocanegra-Valle, A. (2010). "Evaluating and designing materials for ESP classroom." *International LSP journal Iberica* 14(22): 141-166.
2. Harmer, J. (1998). *How to teach English*. Edinburgh Gate, Longman.
3. Hyland, K. (2009). *Teaching and researching writing*. Pearson: Pearson education limited.
4. Litz, D. R. A. (2005). "Textbooks evaluation and ELT management: A South Korean case study." *Asian EFL Journal*: 1-52.